

Effective Teacher-Student Relationship as a Determinant of Business Education Students' Academic Performance in Universities in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Omu, Maureen Roseline¹ & Nwaoburu Blessing (Ph.D)²

Department of Business Education

Faculty of Education

Federal University Otuoke,

Bayelsa State.

omumr@fuotuo.ke.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13826220>

Abstract

The study investigated effective teacher-student relationship as a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa state. The study was guided by two specific objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses. Descriptive survey design was adopted for this study with a population of 149 respondents from two universities in Bayelsa State. No sample and sampling technique was required as the population size was manageable. The instrument for data collection for this study was a self-structured 20-item questionnaire titled "Teacher-students' Relationship and Student Academic Performance Questionnaire (TSRSAPQ)". The instrument's reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha method. Data for research questions were analysed using mean, standard deviation and mean criterion while z-test was used to test the stated hypotheses. The result of the analysed data revealed that predictor variables were active determinants of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State. Based on the findings, the researcher recommends amongst others that; universities in Bayelsa State should incorporate technology in communication by encouraging the use of digital tools presentations, educational videos, and online discussion forums to facilitate clearer and more engaging communication with students.

Keywords: Effective, Teacher-Student Relationship, Business Education, Academic Performance

Introduction

Education is a fundamental human right and a powerful tool for promoting social and economic development in a given society like Nigeria. It helps to reduce poverty, improve health standard, economic, social and environmental well-being and foster a more peaceful, just, and inclusive world. Education has a direct impact on the health and well-being of individuals and communities. Hence, it improves people's health and life expectancy by reducing child and maternal mortality rates, improving nutritional outcomes, and reducing the spread of disease. Education also contributes to economic growth, increases productivity, and helps create more equal and just societies. It empowers individuals, especially women and girls, and reduces inequality. Education is also vital for innovation and technology development, as well as for the protection of the environment. Teachers plays vital roles to ensure that our educational system achieved its objectives in the educational sector. In light of this, diverse studies have proved that no educational

system can rise above the level of its teachers. In the same vein, (Ekechukwu & Ifeanyichukwu, 2021) noted that “teachers play an indispensable role in shaping the future of their students and society at large by instilling values, knowledge, and skills that are beneficial to society.” If teachers are not able to carry out these duties as expected by the society then the quality of education will be headed for disaster (Tai, Omar, Mohammed, Sahari & Khuan, 2017).

Teachers are not only educators, but also mentors, coaches, and role models who inspire and guide their students to success. Without committed and effective teachers, it would be impossible to provide high-quality education and achieve the sustainable educational development goals. Teachers can help students to develop their skills, expand their knowledge and improve their academic performance. Moreover, teachers can foster students’ creativity, critical thinking and problem-solving abilities which are essential for workplace success and beyond. Teachers play vital roles by ensuring that the academic well-being of its students is influenced by the teacher hence students’ poor academic performance could be blamed by school planners and teachers (Egbokhan, 2016).

A student’s academic performance has a profound impact on their future. It can determine the opportunities available to them after graduation, such as the jobs they can get, the salaries they can earn, and the further education they can pursue. Additionally, academic performance can affect a student’s self-esteem and confidence, which can in turn influence their future choices and actions. In short, a student’s academic performance can set the stage for their future success. This could be influenced if there is a positive interaction between the teacher and students. Rabo (2022) found that good teacher-student relationship produces a good environment within the classroom and at the same time creates many benefits for both teachers and students. In contrast, Split, Hughes, Wu and Kwok (2012) are of the view that conflicting relationship causes students to resent, disengage in classroom engagement thereby resulting to distress, insecurity and poor academic performance amongst student

In this research, the following variables on effective teacher-students relationship as determinant of students' academic performance were considered for the study. They are: teachers communication skills and teachers' patience.

Salesman, Masood, Khuan and Hamidah (2019) noted that when teachers are equipped, students’ academic performance will rise, due to rise of other factors that can influence academic performance. Brockman and Russell (2012) asserted that, the 21st century students have clear targets in making educational progress, that they are curious about developing their abilities such as, communication skills that could yield positive impact on their academic pursuit.

Teachers' communication skills as an effective teacher-students' relationship could determine students' academic performance. Communication is the act of transferring ideas, knowledge and information to individuals or groups Ashfague (2020). Communication is key to any solid relationship. Rabo (2022) asserted that most students are unable to communicate and expand their minds as a result of limitations posed in the classroom by their teacher, the researcher added that the opinion of the teacher can be overpowering in most cases and can lead one to forfeit his or her

own opinion, both teachers and students must learn to be patient if they must attain good success in their academic endeavors.

Furthermore, teacher's patience with students as an effective teacher-students' relationship could determine students' academic performance. Patience is a virtue every teacher must possess when relating with students. It allows teacher to respond calmly and compassionately to students' mistakes and difficulties. Schnitzer in Ayes (2017) supported this view and claimed that patience in the most basic sense is the ability of a person to wait calmly in the face of difficulties. Xiodiong (2022) opined that, when students fail to meet teachers' expectations then teachers' patience is tested. However, overtime the teacher's patience is strengthened by experience of students who struggle to meet teachers' expectations, then the teacher learns to use assessment for learning.

From the foregoing, it has been established that teacher's communication skills as well as teacher's patience with students as an effective teacher-students relationship were determinants of students' academic performance. This therefore, predisposes a study on effective teacher-students relationship as a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State for the study.

Statement of the Problem

The academic performance of university students in Bayelsa State has been a growing concern, with many factors being identified as contributors to students' success or failure. Among these, the teacher-student relationship plays a crucial role, particularly in the context of teachers' communication skills and patience. Despite the recognized importance of these factors, there is a lack of empirical studies examining how they specifically influence students' academic outcomes in Bayelsa State universities. Teachers' communication skills are vital for conveying complex concepts and fostering an environment conducive to learning. However, ineffective communication can lead to misunderstandings, decreased student engagement, and ultimately, poor academic performance. Additionally, teachers' patience is essential in managing diverse student needs and learning paces. A lack of patience may result in increased student anxiety, reduced motivation, and lower academic achievement. This study investigated how the quality of teacher-student relationships, with a focus on communication skills and patience, impacts students' academic performance in universities in Bayelsa State.

Purpose of the Study

1. Examine teacher's communication skills as a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State
2. Examine teachers' patience as a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State

Research Questions

1. To what extent is teacher's communication skills a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State

2. To what extent is teacher's patience a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State

Hypotheses

The following hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of teacher's and students in Federal University Otuoke and Niger Delta University on the extent to which teachers' communication skills is a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers and students in Federal University Otuoke and Niger Delta University on the extent to which teachers' patience is a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State.

Significance of the Study

The outcome of this study might be of benefit to the following groups; teachers, educational administrator's, students, curriculum planners and future researchers.

Teachers who may not be willing in relating positively with students might through this study see the benefits associated with relating with students despite their excesses.

Educational administrator's might embrace the need to opt for re-training programs for teachers to sustain their relationship with students.

Students on the other hand who may have been performing low may understand the benefits of having a cordial relationship with their teachers.

Curriculum planners might see the need to create more sensitization programs that will involve both teachers and their students.

Future researchers may also find relevant information from this study that could aid their investigation.

Methods

This study employed a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 18 lecturers and 131 final year students in Federal University Otuoke and Niger Delta University that offers Business Education Program. Thus; a total number of one hundred and forty-nine (149) respondents were used for the study. The instrument for data collection was a self-designed questionnaire of twenty items using four-point rating scale of very high extent (VHE 4) high extent (HE 3) moderate extent (ME 2) and low extent (LE 1) and rated 4,3,2 and 1. The entire copies of the instrument was distributed to respondents with the help of a research assistant. Data was analyzed using arithmetic mean for the research questions, with a criterion mean response score of 2.50 on a four-point rating scale. Thus, any mean response score equal to or above 2.50 was high extent while mean response score below 2.50 was low extent. The null hypotheses was tested

at 0.05 level of significance, any t-calculated value above the t-table value indicated that, the null hypotheses were retained. However, t-calculated value less than t-table value indicated that the null hypotheses were rejected

Results

Research Question 1:

To what extent is teachers' communication skill as an effective teacher-students' relationship a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Teachers and Students for research question one

S/N	Items	Teachers (n=18)			Students (n=131)			Mean Set		
		\bar{X}	SD	Decisio n	\bar{X}	SD	Rmk s	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks
1	Creates a lively classroom climate	2.89	0.57	HE	2.64	0.71	HE	2.77	0.64	HE
2	Stimulates student's curiosity to feel comfortable asking questions	2.50	0.69	HE	2.50	0.72	HE	2.50	0.71	HE
3	Helps improve student's level of understanding of courses	2.39	0.68	HE	2.70	0.84	HE	2.55	0.76	HE
4	Helps students freely express ideas during lesson	2.83	0.37	HE	2.90	0.66	HE	2.87	0.52	HE
5	Helps breakdown concepts during lesson delivery	2.56	0.50	HE	2.84	0.71	HE	2.70	0.60	HE
	Grand	2.63	0.56	HE	2.72	0.73	HE	2.67	0.64	HE
	Mean/SD									

Source: Field Survey Data, 2023 criterion sum = 2.50om

Table 1: it can be seen that with a grand mean set of 2.67 and 0.64 for mean and standard deviation respectively, this indicates that to a **high extent** communication skill was a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in universities in Bayelsa State.

Research question 2:

To what extent is Patience as an effective Teacher-students' relationship a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Teachers and Students for research question two

S/N	Items	Teachers (n=18)			Students (n=131)			Mean Set		
		\bar{X}	SD	Rakes	\bar{X}	SD	Rakes	\bar{X}	SD	Rakes
1	Lack of patience makes students nervous in class	1.89	0.46	ME	1.75	0.85	ME	1.82	0.65	ME

2	Lack of patience makes students insecure in class	1.61	0.49	ME	1.65	0.78	ME	1.63	0.63	ME
3	Lack of patience leads to lack of understanding.	1.83	0.37	ME	1.73	0.82	ME	1.78	0.60	ME
4	Patience makes teacher take time to listen to students concerns	1.39	0.59	ME	1.69	0.77	ME	1.54	0.68	ME
5	Patience makes teacher pay attention to students concerns	1.67	0.75	ME	1.80	0.82	ME	1.73	0.78	ME
	Grand	1.68	0.53	ME	1.72	0.81	ME	1.70	0.67	ME
Mean/SD										

Source: Field Survey Data, 2023

From Table 2, it can be seen that with a grand mean set of 1.70 and 0.67 for mean and standard deviation respectively, this indicates that patience **moderately** determines Business Education students’ academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the scores of teachers and students on communication skills as an effective Teacher-students’ relationship a determinant of Business Education students’ academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State

Table 5: z-test of Difference between Teachers and Students on the extent communication skills as an effective Teacher-students’ relationship is a determinant of Business Education students’ academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State

Respondents	Mean	S. D	N	S. E	z-Cal.	z-Crit.	Remark
Teachers	2.63	0.56	18	0.15	0.564	1.984	Accept
Students	2.72	0.73	131				

The analysis of Table 5 showed that z-calculated value of 0.564 is less than the z-critical value of 1.984 and as such the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the scores of teachers and students on classroom engagement as an effective Teacher-students relationship a determinant of Business Education students’ academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State is accepted. This implies that both Teachers and Students agree that to a high extent communication skill as an effective Teacher-students’ relationship is a determinant of Business Education students’ academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the scores of teachers and students on patience as an effective Teacher-students’ relationship a determinant of Business Education students’ academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State

Table 6: z-test of Difference between Teachers and Students on the extent patience as an effective Teacher-students' relationship is a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State

Respondents	Mean	S. D	N	S. E	z-Cal.	z-Crit.	Remark
Teachers	1.68	0.53	18	0.14	0.309	1.984	Accept
Students	1.72	0.81	131				

The analysis of Table 6 showed that z-calculated value of 0.309 is less than the z-critical value of 1.984 and as such the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the scores of teachers and students on patience as an effective Teacher-students relationship a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State is accepted. This implies that both Teachers and Students agree that to moderate extent patience as an effective Teacher-student's relationship is a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from the analysis of research question one showed that to a high extent communication skill as an effective Teacher-students relationship is a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State. This is evident as communication skills: creates a livelier classroom climate; stimulates students' curiosity to feel comfortable asking questions; helps improve student's level of understanding of courses; helps students freely express ideas during lesson and helps breakdown concepts during lesson delivery. This is confirmed by the acceptance the first null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the scores of teachers and students on communication kills as an effective Teacher-students relationship a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State. The finding of this paper is in agreement with the findings of Brockman and Russell (2012) and Wahgudi (2022) who asserted that, the 21st century students have clear targets in making educational progress, that they are curious about developing their abilities such as, communication skills that could yield positive impact on their academic pursuit.

The findings from the analysis of research question two showed that to moderate extent patience as an effective Teacher-students relationship is a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State. This is evident as lack of patience: makes students nervous in class; makes students insecure in class; leads to lack of understanding; patience makes teacher take time to listen to students concerns and pay attention to students concerns. This is confirmed by the acceptance the third null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the scores of teachers and students on patience as an effective Teacher-students' relationship a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State. This finding is in consonance with the findings of Brown et al. (2018) and Syider and Frasyimiuk (2020) whose study found that teachers' patience can influence the

process of teaching, tolerance of the unexpected and ability to persevere till the end of the instructional delivery achievement.

Conclusion

The empirical evidence does show that student-teacher relationships are very important for students and teachers in both learning and teaching as it is a determinant of Business Education students' academic performance in Universities in Bayelsa State. Furthermore, teachers must develop good communication skills, and learn to exercise patience with learners during lesson delivery in order to gain their attention and inculcate expected knowledge to them.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following were recommended amongst others

1. Universities in Bayelsa State should incorporate technology in communication by encouraging the use of digital tools presentations, educational videos, and online discussion forums to facilitate clearer and more engaging communication with students.
2. Government should collaborate with communication experts, organise periodic training on mindfulness and stress management that could help them maintain patience in challenging situations, thereby fostering a more supportive learning environment.

References

- Ashfague, A.S, Zumaya, F.S & Sehrish, N. (2020). University student communication skills as a determinant of academic achievement: *Sir Byed Journal of Educational Social Research* 3(2) 107-144
- Ayse, E.B., Gokham, I. (2017). Effect of the patience training programme on patience and well-being levels of university students 6(1), 2324 – 8068.
- Brockman M.S. & Russell, S.T. (2012). Academic success building partner for youth National 4th council and the university of Arizona, Achieved on October 10, 2023. <https://calscf.calsnet.arizona.edu/fes/bpy/contents.cfm?>
- Egbokhan, B. (2016). executive stress and inoculation: a lecture not in industrial psychology. Federal polytechnic Bauchi.
- Ekechukwu, P.C. and Ifenyichukwu; J.M (2020). Principal – staff relationship for effective secondary school's administration in south – south geo – political zone of Nigeria. *International journal of progressive and technologies.*
- Hughes, J. & Crook O. (2013). Influence of Student teacher and parent teachers' relationship on lower achieving readers' engagement and engagement and achievement and in the primary grades. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 99(1) 39-51.
- Rabo, M. (2022). Teacher student relationship as a tool for positive academic performance in Nigeria, *British Journal of multidisciplinary and advanced studies: education, learning, training and development* 2 (1) 42-53
- Salesman, M. W., Khan, W.B. & Bing, hey (2019) investigating the relationship between teacher quality and student academic performance with empowerment as a mediator; *journal of contemporary issues through* (a), 61 – 74).

- Spilt, J.L, Hughes, J.N, Wu, J.Y. & Kwok, O. (2012). Dynamics of teacher-student relationship: stability and change across elementary school and the influence on children's academic success child development, 83(4). 1180 – 1195.
- Tai, M.K, Omar, A.K, Mohamed S.N. & Khuan, W.B. (2017). Principal change leadership competencies and teacher attitudes towards change: The mediating effects of teacher change beliefs. *International Journal of Leadership in education*, 1 – 20.
- Xiaodiong, Z. (2022). The role of teacher patience in the implementation of assessment for learning (AFL): Vignettes from a writing classroom. *Journal of Humanities and Social sciences communication*, 4(7), 69 – 78.